

THE RELEVANCE OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT “SAFETY OF LIFE ACTIVITY” IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880159>

Abstract. *In this article, the impact of the science “safety of life activity” on the types of labor activities on insos is aimed at solving practical work, their treatment for development with the help of basic structural elements of the teaching method, advanced technologies.*

Keywords: *labor protection, collective agreement, modification of labor activity, working conditions.*

It is established that any construction facilities cannot be accepted for use and put into operation if they do not have a security certificate issued in accordance with the procedure established by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Enterprises that must be registered in accordance with the established procedure must submit in advance a certificate providing for the implementation of the activities provided by the relevant supervisory authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The procedure for obtaining the specified permit of the enterprise is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The activities of enterprises that do not meet the requirements of Labor security and provide security for the health and life of workers, or the use of production facilities, until they are made in accordance with the requirements of Labor security, are suspended by authorized agencies in the manner established in the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The rapid penetration of scientific and technical Combs in production, in addition to the release from hard labor, makes it possible to fully improve their working conditions, reduce accidents, and, moreover, increase work efficiency. In the process of physical labor, a person achieves the transformation of his form and essence by influencing one body with the help of a weapon of Labor. The effect of this labor, in addition to the weapon of Labor and the essence of the work, again depends on the temperature and illumination of the workplace, tidiness and order, air purity and the absence of noise, and a number of similar factors, all of which together represent the working conditions. Thus, it is said that the working condition is the sum of the factors of productivity that can affect a person's health and work activity during labor, and they will consist of 6 manifestations, as in this drawing. Now it is from these factors of working conditions that the causes of unfortunate accidents that occur in production are conditionally divided into six groups.

1. Organizational reasons include the lack of timely implementation of safety rules, training and explanation, the absence of work Organization projects and technical control in construction, the dissatisfaction of the workplace, the inability of jomakors and protective equipment to meet labor demand, etc.

2. Technical reasons, on the other hand, include a series of reasons, namely, errors made in the project, violation or imperfection of the work order, the reason for deviations from the project and the absence or failure of equipment and auxiliary devices and obstacles, the absence of security tools on the machines, or their lack of timely repair, lack of control, etc. Working conditions Health

and cleanliness, non-compliance of working conditions with sanitary and aesthetic requirements, non-compliance with climatic and light requirements, air pollution, noise Suran refers to such as the height from the norm, the presence of the risk of harmful radiation, lack of culture in relation to work and the next colleague, the lack of arrangement of the workplace and the fact that it is not equipped in compliance with safety requirements. Social causes include violation of labor discipline and the mental balance of others, the absence of mutual consequence among the public due to pride and manliness, and the like.

Examples of mental-physiological causes are physical weakness of the weak will of the employee, the severity and continuity of Labor, the discomfort of the employee's state and movement in the labor process, etc. When production accidents are analyzed in relation to these causes, it will be possible to prevent their recurrence.

Working conditions

But just as such a development cannot be achieved without deep knowledge and sound technique, it is impossible to imagine without risk any new technique and the procedure process associated with its use. The main methodological task of the topic is to develop in production the conditions of work, the procedure process, the development of entrepreneurs who can be able to prevent misfortune, relying on scientific analysis and conclusions arising from it in terms of the possibility of causing accidents of work equipment. Until this time, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge. Such a method would quench independent thinking, creative search, initiative in students. Educators-scientists have been working in the educational system for years, “Why do we teach? What do we teach? How do we teach? in addition to the search for answers to the questions “how to teach effectively and efficiently?” were looking for an answer. This has led scholars and practitioners to believe that the process of learning can be attempted to technologize, a technological process that gives a clearly guaranteed result regarding the production of teaching. In different countries of the world, many researchers have always researched the application of innovation in education. They collected good information about “innovation”

, “interactive methods”, innovative technologies. In the following years, scientific and methodological research on the implementation of Independent Education on the basis of

innovation and Information Technology and experiments on the implementation of Education show that this problem can be solved. For example, in the implementation of Independent Education of students on the basis of innovative technology "Mental attack", "Pinboard", "cluster", "design", "assessment", "Keys-stadi" technologies. The application of innovations to the educational process today requires the implementation of the following tasks:

- determination of the exact purpose of the academic discipline;
- determination of the size and content of science;
- development and recommendation of the necessary educational technologies;
- creation of material and technical support of science;
- study of the characteristics of learners;
- teacher training and lesson design.

It is permissible to dwell on the following information on innovative pedagogical technologies for the use of innovations in foreign education.

Today, as a result of the emergence of ideas of a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and updating the educational jaraèn, a new direction in the pedagogical activity of the pedagogue also appeared the concept of "innovative activity of the pedagogue". Concepts such as innovation in pedagogy, innovative activity, innovative pedagogy, management of innovative jaraèns in education appeared in the 60s of the 20th century at the very beginning, in the countries of the United States and Western Europe - at a time when the concept of educational technology was recognized. At that time, the center and Institute for pedagogical innovation was established in Europe. An analysis of sources providing information about the emergence of these concepts and the creation of an innovative educational theory shows that these concepts arose as a result of the establishment of the educational system by technologizing the educational system, introducing pedagogical technologies into the educational system, improving educational efficiency, ensuring the socialization of the individual, making room for the formation.

I.Schumpater and N.Kondratevs-if they are considered the first and greatest theorists of the concept of innovation, K.Angelovsky, V.A Slastenin and V.I.In their scientific research, slobadchikov tried to prove that innovative activity is a special form of pedagogical activity, and scientists who have achieved certain results in this regard are recognized as such. In Particular, V.I.Slobadchikov writes:

- First of all, innovative activities cannot be likened to activities in the field of scientific creativity, because such an analogy

- The term innovative activity makes the meaning shallow. Because any scientific and technical activity is innovative in its nature. Therefore, it is necessary to consider innovative activities in a certain area of social practice.

This practice can be considered innovative from the point of view of the concrete subject and any activity that leads to serious changes in relation to the current tradition

Innovation (Eng. Innovation-innovation input) - is defined as changing the internal structure of the system. Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, a system of action of social entities aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object. There are different approaches and opinions on the creation of the essence of this theory of ideas, and there is no single opinion on its essence in science. Innovations are relevant, important, new approaches formed in one system. They are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations and are promising for the development of educational content, and also have a positive effect on the development of

the educational system as a whole. Innovation is the last result that is known to lead to much more success than before, when technology, forms and methods in a certain field of activity or production, a new approach to solving a problem or applying a new technological process. Today, the following classification of innovations in the educational system is approved:

1. Depending on the direction of activity (in pedagogical jaraèn, in management).
2. According to the description of the introduced changes (radical, modified, combined).
3. According to the scale of changes (local, modular, systematic).
4. According to the source of origin (for the same team, the interior is taken from the outside).

In each society, the purpose of personality formation is determined, and in accordance with it, a pedagogical system must exist. The existing system is also inevitable to change if the goal changes. The national cadre training program has made it the main goal to educate citizens who feel responsible to society, the state and the family. Chunonchi, the national program is considered a state order in the field of education and fully corresponds to the essence and content of the ideology of national independence. Only the public order of Education, which clearly defines the general goals and objectives of Austria, guarantees the conditions of existence of the pedagogical system for higher education. Pedagogical technology is such an area of knowledge that, through them, in the new millennium, a fundamental turn will take place in the state's education sector, the activity of a teacher (educator) will be renewed, a system of hurtful thinking, humanitarian feelings will be formed in students.

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